

UERJ - CMS Group

Thematic areas: Electroweak Physics, Forward Physics,
Flavor Physics, BSM, Instrumentation and Computing

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Abstract

UERJ CMS group is composed of several subgroups studying different aspects of the rich CMS physics spectrum. We have subgroups working on Higgs physics , Forward Physics , Heavy Flavours and BSM. We also have many ongoing activities on hardware and software development , the main ones being the Precision Proton Spectrometer (PPS) , the Resistive Plate Chamber (RPC) upgrade and the development of the forward muon L1 trigger based on neural network implemented on a FPGA.

measurement of Higgs production through vector boson fusion (VBF) and it's couplings to detect possible deviations associated with new physics. Another process we will be measuring is the vector boson scattering (VBS) that has a similar topology to the VBF. There is a delicate balance between the VBS process diagrams in order to ensure the unity of the Standard Model processes. The presence of new physics can alter the balance between VBS diagrams and lead to observable deviations. These analyzes will be developed using modern deep neural network techniques in order to optimize the significance of the observed signal. We are also developing with Fermilab an L1 level trigger for the CMS front muon system, based on deep neural networks implemented in FPGA.

The Precision Proton Spectrometer (PPS) system is composed of a set of detectors for measuring protons and flight time of protons from collisions in the CMS experiment. The PPS was built to measure Central Production processes Exclusive, including the production via fusion of W bosons pairs of photons and Z, pairs of photons and high mass leptons and high transverse momentum jets, as well as search for anomalous and new engagements resonances. PPS detector is already in operation and collected data at high luminance integrated with the CMS. During the LHC shutdown period from 2019, improvements will be made to the PPS system, its electronics and data acquisition system (DAQ) included. In this project we propose to emulate the electronic PPS on a test bench. The bench will be used for the development and commissioning of the new DAQ system. The group participates in the analysis of the data collected with the PPS detector involving the measurement of gauge boson pair production via photon fusion, which provides information on the theory's quartic quadratic couplings. When measuring protons from interaction with PPS, the sensitivity for measuring quartic couplings increases significantly, including the anomalous couplings described in effective theories (EFT) used in extensions to the Standard Model.

1 Scientific Context

This document describes the research activities related UERJ - CMS group on physics analysis related to Higgs Physics, Forward Physics , Heavy Flavors and BSM as well as hardware and software development for the Precision Proton Spectrometer (PPS) , the Resistive Plate Chamber (RPC) upgrade and the development of the forward muon L1 trigger.

The CMS experiment was designed to detect events characteristic of the Standard Model as well as physics that goes beyond it. It is able to accurately identify and measure muons, photons, electrons and jets over a wide energy range and with wide angular coverage at high or low light. An overview of the CMS detector and its sub-detectors is presented in the following figure. The CMS experiment also offers opportunities for the study of frontal and low-x physics, including photon-photon physics , which have aroused interest especially in the LHC when associated with the production of new particles or anomalous phenomena in relation to the Standard Model.

The UERJ HEP group has a long term involvement within the CMS experiment at CERN and we are committed to the physics program of the CMS experiment. The LHC accelerator at CERN plays a central role in the exploration of particle physics and CERN will continue to lead the field in next decades with the HL-LHC upgrade and future accelerators like the FCC.

2 Objectives

UERJ HEP group will engage in various research activities, divided between physics data analysis, software development and hardware development. These software and hardware activities are critical to enable data analysis in high energy physics and detector operation. Below we present these activities in more detail.

2.1 Higgs Physics Analysis and Vector Boson Scattering

Detecting the Higgs boson is a highly complex task from an experimental point of view. The Higgs production cross section is extremely small and there is a wide variety of processes that have an experimental final state signature very similar to that of the Higgs. These processes often have much larger cross sections than Higgs and create important backgrounds that make it difficult to detect the Higgs signal. During the Run 1 data collection the CMS experiment collected a brightness in excess of 20 fb⁻¹ during 2011 and 2012. After a period of detector and accelerator upgrades between 2013 and 2014 the experiment began the new Run 2 data taking, during which it collected about 150 fb⁻¹.

Among the various Higgs decay modes, vector boson decay is one of the most interesting channels for measuring its properties by the ease of identification of the final state and the high decay ratio.

Fusion of vector bosons (VBF) is a process that stands out among the various modes of production of Higgs by presenting a comparatively high section of shock and a relatively low background among other modes of production. This is due to the distinctive feature of the VBF process that has the presence of two energetic and

frontal jets associated with the emission of vector bosons as shown in the diagram below.

Another associated process that we also propose to measure is vector boson scattering (VBS) which has a similar topology to VBF and is also connected to the electroweak symmetry breaking mechanism and the Higgs mechanism. In the electroweak theory, the VBS process is mediated by the diagrams involving the Higgs exchange and diagrams involving the exchange of vector bosons, which have a delicate balance to ensure the unity of the process. Higgs-mediated diagrams cancel divergences of scattering diagrams involving triple boson coupling (TGC) and quartic boson coupling (QGC) ensuring a finite result. Despite the discovery of the 125 GeV Higgs, signs of new physics may still be hidden in the electroweak symmetry breaking sector. The presence of new physics may alter the balance between the VBS diagrams and consequently lead to observable deviations in scattering. For this purpose we intend to directly measure the invariant mass spectrum of dibosons produced from VBS. This is a striking test for the electroweak symmetry breaking mechanism, as it is possible that the Higgs sector is more complex than the Standard Model suggests, where there are other particles involved in the unitarization of vector boson scattering. According to studies already carried out, the observation of a signal with significance of three sigmas will require an integrated brightness of at least 100 fb⁻¹, which is the level of brightness that we will soon reach.

2.2 Photon-Photon Physics and Anomalous Quartic Couplings

The PPS system allows, among others, the measurement of scattered protons in exclusive production processes of gauge boson pairs. $W + W -$ boson pair production diagram via photon fusion. The exclusive production of W bosons, $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow W + W -$, was measured by CMS collaboration with 7 and 8 TeV data without the use of low angle scattered proton detectors [15]. From these results, limits were extracted for the $\gamma\gamma WW$ quartic anomalous couplings, which were quite significant in relation to other channels studied in the LHC. The inclusion of scattered proton information in this type of process considerably increases the sensitivity for measuring the unique process $\gamma\gamma W + W -$ and coupling $\gamma\gamma WW$, as detailed in Ref. [3]. We will consider the channels in which the W bosons decay into leptons and neutrinos and also the channel in which one of the W bosons decays in jets (semileptonic channel). In a kinematic region looking for anomalous couplings, W bosons are typically energetic, resulting in two small angular separation jets and effective detection of a substructure jet. The exclusive production of Z boson pairs, ie the $\gamma\gamma \rightarrow ZZ$ process, has not been observed to date. Since the $\gamma\gamma ZZ$ quartic coupling does not exist in the Standard Model, the identification of few such events in a reduced background scenario may indicate the existence of anomalous couplings and therefore a hint of physics beyond the Standard Model. Decay channels in four leptons and when one of the Z bosons decays in jets provide experimental signatures with high identification and reconstruction efficiency and reduced background. With a data sample of 100 fb⁻¹, it is expected that a sensitivity far exceeding the current limits for the $\gamma\gamma ZZ$ quadratic anomalous couplings is expected.

2.3 SUSY Search In Compressed Scenarios

The search for supersymmetry (SUSY) has been performed for many years in several collider experiments, including the LHC and CMS. So far no evidence has been found for SUSY. If nature is supersymmetric, it can only mean that: SUSY particle masses are even larger than the current energies reached by the collider allow us to test; The production shock sections of SUSY are much smaller than those predicted by theory; The mass spectrum of SUSY particles is compressed. In this case, even with considerably high shock sections, such compressed SUSY (cSUSY) compressed SUSY) would not be detected with data analysis that has been done so far. Based on this last point, an analysis of cSUSY search data was initiated. The analysis is based on a cSUSY signal, where two gluinos are created, which have a sufficiently long lifespan that causes these gluinos to brown before they decay. When hadronized, each gluino produces an R-hadron, which in turn decays into two Squarks and a $\xi 1$ type neutrino (known as Lightest Supersymmetric Particle, or LSP). Data analysis consists of searching for cSUSY events with displaced vertices (resulting from the decay of R-hadrons), four jets, missing energy (or MET due to neutraline), and an early state radiation (ISR) jet. Initial State Radiation), which can help in selecting signal events, since their energy is higher compared to the other four jets of the event, which may have such low energy that they will not be reconstructed.

2.4 PPS - Precision Proton Spectrometer

The Precision Proton Spectrometer (PPS) detector system has been installed and integrated into the CMS experiment during the LHC Run 2 data taking period. It is a joint project by the CMS and TOTEM collaborations with the capability of measuring protons scattered at very small angles, operating at high instantaneous luminosity. The scattered protons remain inside the beam pipe, displaced from the central beam orbit, and can be measured by detectors placed inside movable beam pipe insertions, called Roman pots (RP), which approach the beam down to a few mm . The PPS detectors have collected data corresponding to an integrated luminosity larger than $100 fb^{-1}$ during the LHC Run 2, from 2016–2018.

The PPS detector allows the study of central exclusive production (CEP), the process $pp \rightarrow p + X + p$, by detecting at least one of the outgoing protons. In the CEP process, one or both protons may dissociate into a low-mass state (p^*); when both protons dissociate no signal can be seen in the PPS detectors. The central system X may be formed by W and Z boson pairs, as well as photon and lepton pairs, high-pt jet production, and other high-mass states. The CEP process may occur through a gluon-gluon colour-singlet exchange and by photon-photon fusion. The diagram of the latter process is shown in Figure ??.

Figure ?? shows the layout of the RP stations installed at around $210m$ from the CMS interaction point (IP5), along the beam line in LHC sector 56. A symmetric configuration is installed in LHC sector 45. The stations are comprised of RPs that approach the beam vertically from the top and bottom, and horizontally. During standard machine operation, scattered protons feature a large displacement in the horizontal direction and a small vertical displacement at the RP positions. The horizontal RPs are hence used. The vertical RPs are used in special configurations of the ma-

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the photon-photon fusion process. The centrally produced system may consist of lepton, photon, W or Z boson pairs, or other particles.

chine and in low intensity proton-proton fills for the calibration and alignment of the detectors.

Each detector arm consists of two RPs instrumented with silicon tracking detectors that measure the transverse displacement of protons with respect to the beam, and one RP station with timing detectors to measure their time-of-flight. The measurement of the difference between the arrival times of protons in the stations on both sides of the IP with high precision rejects background combinations with protons from pileup interactions, or beam-halo particles. Silicon strip sensors with a reduced insensitive region in the edge facing the beam have initially been used. An RP hosts 10 silicon strip sensor planes, half at a $+45^\circ$ angle and half at a -45° angle with respect to the bottom of the RP. These sensors cannot sustain a large radiation dose and cannot identify multiple tracks measured in the same event. They have for this reason been gradually replaced by new 3D silicon pixel sensors, with one RP station during the 2017 data taking run, and both RP tracking stations in 2018. Each RP hosts 6 3D pixel sensor planes. The timing detectors consisted of single- and double-sided single-crystal CVD diamond sensor planes, with one plane of ultra-fast silicon sensors during the 2017 data taking.

PPS upgrade for Run 3 and HL-LHC

During the LHC Run 3, the PPS detectors will use similar technologies. The detector system will consist of two RP tracking stations with 3D pixel sensors per arm, with an upgraded front-end electronics. The timing system will be upgraded with the goal of achieving a resolution of $30ps$ per arm. A second RP station will be installed on each arm, each housing 4 planes of double-sided diamond sensors. The readout of the timing sensors will be upgraded for improved performance and radiation damage mitigation.

With the LHC long shutdown after Run 3, the section around the CMS IP will be redesigned and the PPS stations removed. A new PPS system is currently under study for HL-LHC, with potential station locations at $195 - 235m$ from the IP, and at the $420m$ location previously studied in the FP420 project. The latter would allow to measure systems with two tagged protons down to masses of $m_X \lesssim 50GeV$, such as

Figure 2: Schematic layout of the beam line between the interaction point and the location of the RP stations in LHC sector 56, corresponding to the negative z direction in the CMS coordinate system and the outgoing proton in the clockwise beam direction. The accelerator elements are indicated. The 210-near, 210-far, 220-far and timing stations where PPS detectors have been installed are marked in red. The 210-near and 210-far tracking stations have been used in the 2016 data taking, and the 210-far and 220-far stations in 2017 and 2018. Timing detectors were operational in 2017 and 2018.

central exclusive Higgs production. The near stations would increase the high-mass PPS acceptance up to 2.7TeV . An evolution of the sensor technologies is foreseen, with 3D pixel detectors for tracking and diamond and ultra-fast silicon detectors for timing measurements.

The UERJ CMS group has had a leading role in the funding, development and operation of the current PPS system. The UERJ group currently expects to contribute to the development of the new PPS DAQ system, as well as to the characterization and tests of radiation-hard ultra-fast silicon detectors as a possible sensor technology for the PPS timing detectors at HL-LHC.

2.5 RPC Upgrade

The muon RPC Upgrade project consists of installation of a new Link System for the RPC system and new RPC chambers in the high eta regions. This project will be finished with the installation of the new RPC chambers and electronics during the Yearly Technical Stops at the end of 2022 and 2023. We are working in the standard maintenance of the detector, during LS2 and also have participated in software activities as: RPC online software upgrade and maintenance, update of the readout software for Run3, and the RPC data certification using Machine Learning (ML) techniques to evaluate performance using autoencoder. The RPC Upgrade phase II is a perfect project for integration of our group with CMS collaboration. It offers the possibility to scale up the Brazilian contribution to the experiment and creates possible expertise and training opportunities for our group. Besides this, it also serves as a working project for new HEP laboratories and, since it is strictly muon related, it directly affects the experiment and increases the efficiency of the physics objects related to the analysis.

The RIO group will share the responsibility to develop: 1) The online software to control and monitor the RPC Front End boards and the new Link System; 2) A

new Data Quality Monitoring for the online monitoring of the detector performance; The plan is to build in RIO a laboratory fully equipped with all electronics and set-up needed to develop and validate the new software. After the development phase, the RIO group will deploy the software for production in CMS. In addition the group will be involved in the commissioning of the full system.

2.6 Neural Network based Frontal Muon L1 Trigger

One of CMS's most challenging goals when taking data in the future high-light accelerator regime (HL-LHC) is to maintain physical acceptance for all L1 trigger level basic physics objects, leptons, photons, jets, and MET. To achieve this goal, it is essential to introduce a new L1 level front muon trigger. The highest expected occupations in HL-LHC operation and the extremely low latencies required on the L1 (around 10 us) present an unprecedented set of technological challenges. Our group is involved in a joint project with LPC-FERMILAB to develop the front muon detector Trigger L1, based on a deep neural network (DNN) implemented in FPGA. This trigger will increase the geometric acceptance as well as more accurate measurements in the high light regime. This will be of great importance to the physics studies proposed in this project. This hardware project is based on HLS4ML software developed at FERMI-LAB. It is able to automatically synthesize a software-implemented neural network from the Python language (eg KERAS) into one directly in the FPGA. HLS4ML supports a variety of network architectures (DNN, CNN, RNN and LTSM) and allows adjustment of network parameters for performance studies in different applications. The main challenge in this implementation is to match the network size to the resources available in the FPGA where Digital Signal Processor (DSP) blocks are used for multiplication and their number is the largest limiting factor of the network size that can be synthesized. The front muon trigger L1 involves three main steps: pattern recognition to find the path points in the 4 muon stations, the path adjustment associated with the points, and the determination of the muon momentum associated with the path. In a broader perspective, with this work we will be developing expertise in advanced topics related to deep neural networks (DNN), Machine Learning and its implementation in hardware from FPGA, which has great technological appeal and scientific.

3 List of Scientists

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4 Construction and operational costs

The budget for construction of the Roman Pots and RPC are described in the table below, where values are quoted are in KCHF

PROJECT	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3	YEAR 4	YEAR 5
RPC	270.00	260.00	240.00	240.00	
PPS	356.55	356.55	656.55	684.83	456.55
TOTAL (3292.75 =)	626.55	616.55	896.55	696.55	456.55